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Understanding international students' barriers in their first-year at a U.S. university

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ABSTRACT

International students in the United States face several challenges when transitioning into college. The purpose of this paper is to understand how international students perceive the barriers they face in their first year attending college in the United States and to learn about the resources international students are utilizing for support. Data were collected qualitatively through individual interviews with 6 first-year international students. Data were transcribed and analysed using thematic analysis procedures. Results suggest that the barriers international engineering students face when attending college in the United States are complex and are summarized in terms of academic challenges, social and emotional adaptability, cultural clashes, and relationships with domestic students. Our findings provide implications for engineering education research on how to study international students' barriers, for practice on how to make first year classrooms more inclusive, and for advising on how to provide support that is required for international students.

1. INTRODUCTION

The international student population in the United States (U.S.) has been growing considerably in the last decades. This population is important because of the unique assets they bring into the classrooms by providing a variety of insights coming from their early academic and life experiences in their home countries [1-4]. Furthermore,

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STEM programs rely considerably on international students, especially at the graduate level. Though it varies between institutions, in the last two years there has been an overall decrease in the international student enrolment at U.S. institutions. Hence, there is a need to provide a more positive experience for current international students in order to increase their attraction to higher education institutions in the U.S. and in order to increase the quality of their experience.

International students face at least three major barriers when coming to the U.S. to attend college: (i) engaging in a new social and academic environment [2, 5], (ii) in some cases, using English as a second language and in academic settings [5, 6], and (iii) experiencing “culture shock” relating to American culture and academic culture of higher education institutions [1, 2]. Although extensive research has been conducted on international students [2, 3, 7-12], there are no studies as far as we know that analyse the challenges of first-year international students while also exploring the support systems utilized to increase the engagement and motivation of this population at their new institution.

Extensive research has been done on how to increase students’ motivation and engagement in higher education. Engagement is seen as an important part of learning [13-15]. Students need to feel a sense of belonging within their academic program in order to effectively develop their identities as future professionals. Sense of belonging has been directly linked to successful outcomes in academic programs including persistence, self-efficacy, and perceptions of technical competence [16-18].

One purpose of this study is to understand how international students perceive the barriers they face in their first year attending college in the U.S. Another purpose is to learn about the resources international students are utilizing for support and use this knowledge to create more effective supports for this population of students. The primary research question that guided this study is:

RQ1: How do international students identify the barriers faced in their first year of college in the United States?

To answer the research question, data were collected qualitatively with international students attending their first semester of college at a large research institution in the United States. Sense of belonging was used as the theoretical framework to guide this study.

2. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

2.1. Sense of Belonging

Studies suggest that students become more engaged when they feel as though they belong. Carini, et al. [15] argue that research has demonstrated that student engagement is linked positively to desirable learning outcomes in students such as critical thinking and good grades. Understanding the importance of engagement, we also recognize that students become engaged with their academic program and their institution when they feel they belong. Floyd-Smith, et al. [19] explain that developing

sense of belonging includes the development of a community where students can participate and interact with others. The authors developed a conceptual framework that emphasizes the impact of sense of belonging and academic outcomes for students in undergraduate education. According to Floyd-Smith, et al. [19] when students are engaged (i.e. feel they belong) they will also demonstrate intrinsic motivation. This engagement will lead to short-term and long-term positive academic and affective outcomes. It becomes crucial for the international students in the U.S. to find communities, and significant experiences to positively engage with their academic programs and their institution. Extensive research has been conducted on the importance of developing positive relationships, engaging in out-of-the classroom learning experiences, and feeling included as a member of an academic community to promote students' engagement that lead to short and long term positive outcomes [17, 23, 24].

Participation in extracurricular activities is another factor that leads to increased academic success. Wilson, et al. [23] explain that research suggests that when the student participation in extracurricular activities is voluntary, students have higher levels of “academic conscientiousness,” (p.627) which the authors define as a willingness to raise their standards for academic performance. This includes how they perform in the classroom, understand class materials, but also is related to how they conduct research, and help and interact with classmates. The expectation is that students can develop short-term academic outcomes such as improving their critical thinking, problem solving, and research skills, developing productive relationships with their peers and mentors, and performing well in the classes they are enrolled. Some of the long-term academic outcomes that students can develop are to become engaged professionals who are able to successfully finish their academic program and effectively adapt to their first professional job.

According to Allendoerfer, et al. [18] providing students with opportunities to belong helps them overcome some of the needs they face during their time in college, and provides “the most return of investment for engagement in academic endeavours” (p. 512). The authors suggest that the most important part of providing sense of belonging and engagement are activities that enable students to receive family-like support, such as [18] (p.531):

- Formal cohorts of incoming students in classroom and/or labs
- Living/learning communities, such as residence halls
- Design teams/lab partners, scaffolded for success with respect to the team relationships as well as the project goals
- Weekly informal gatherings with faculty and students for non-academic reasons (e.g., departmental tea, lunches in the dining halls, etc.)
- Service learning opportunities
- Academically-related clubs, with space to meet and ‘hang out’ to facilitate community

Many of these suggestions are included in first-year programs in most Universities in the U.S., however, these programs are created for the U.S. context. For international students these initiatives might require additional efforts since they might face different barriers that prevent them from taking advantage of interventions created to welcome students into college.

Furthermore, learning environments that foster a sense of belonging offer more opportunity for students to learn in a more socially-complex manner. Baxter-Magolda [20] explains that knowledge is socially constructed based on interactions between the “self” and peers. Therefore, learning environments designed to promote mutual construction of knowledge will also promote self-authorship providing students with the opportunity to develop strong skills to learn and adapt knowledge to different situations –a desired skill for any profession. Candy [21] explains that learning is rarely a phenomenon that occurs entirely individually, rather it usually occurs in the context of social grouping. It becomes important to understand how to better provide social experiences that lead to international students’ sense of belonging.

3. METHODS

A qualitative approach was used in this study to answer our research question. We used a case study as the methodological framework to explore the barriers international first-year students experience when attending college in the United States. Case study research is based on the examination of the context and every complex condition in the real-world setting of the phenomenon in order to have an integral understanding of it [26]. The unit of analysis for the case study are 6 first-year international students. We made this methodological decision because our goal was to better understand the students’ experiences in their first year of college in terms of the barriers the students face which is considered a complex phenomenon.

3.1. Participants

Participants in this study were 6 international students in their first semester attending college in the U.S. from the following countries: China (2), India (2), Brazil (1), Vietnam (1). Four students are male (China, India, Brazil, and Vietnam) and two students are female (China, India). Each student participated in a semi-structured interview during the Fall semester 2018. Following IRB approval, participants were recruited via email. All participants received a \$15 (USD) gift card upon completion of the interview and all interviews were audio-recorded and transcribed verbatim.

3.2. Data collection

The interview protocol utilized in the semi-structured interviews was piloted and contained questions about the experiences of international students during their first semester at a large, four-year research institution. Prompts focused on eliciting concrete descriptions of students’ first week and month in the United States, experiences with their classes, developing friendships, and adapting to the new culture. The questions also asked the students to reflect and compare how their experience could have been different if they were U.S. students. Interviews lasted no

more than 45 minutes and were conducted in a place mutually agreed upon by the interviewer and the student. Students signed a consent form prior to participation.

3.3. Data analysis

Data analysis was conducted by three members of the research team using the thematic analysis approach outlined by Robson and McCartan [22]. Thematic analysis uses individual experiences, interpretations, realities, and discourse as avenues for exploring the group to which the individual belongs [22, 23]. For this study, thematic analysis provided a means to understanding barriers that international students might face as constructed through the experiences and interpretations of our participants.

Transcripts were analysed using line-by-line open-coding to allow codes to emerge from the data. “In Vivo” coding was deemed appropriate since using the words from the participants, their terms and conceptualizations, is more likely to accurately capture the participants’ experience [25]. Codes were then grouped into themes to support both within- and cross-participant analyses. Our themes were guided by the codes that emerged most often. Dedoose qualitative software was used to conduct the analysis and to identify patterns among the researchers.

3.4. Limitations

The study limitations are related to the transferability of the findings. Since the participants are a small sample, it might not be representative of all international students. In addition, results should be considered with caution as the students’ experiences represent a specific institution. Other Universities may utilize different approaches to support international students as they transition into their first year. Another limitation with regard to language proficiency is that all participants speak English as a second language. In some cases, the authors had to adjust student responses based on interview notes because the transcripts could not be understood. We recognize that some of the students’ experiences could have been lost by language translation.

3.5. Measures of research quality

Limitations were mitigated by having a set of procedures to ensure the results were of quality. Firstly, multiple coders met and agreed on analysis suggested in qualitative inquiry [25]. The coders met to discuss the early stages of data analysis. An agreement was reached after having discussions on initial differences in coding to increase the trustworthiness of the results. The credibility of the findings was determined to be aided by the immediacy of the interview. Students were interviewed in their first weeks at the University, allowing the interviews to capture their initial experiences promptly. The confirmability of the results was strengthened further in two ways. Coding was conducted by three authors, ensuring codes were not only decided by one author at any given time. In addition, data analysis was discussed collaboratively and results were deliberated by the three authors.

4. RESULTS

In answering the research question, our results clearly determined patterns in the responses of the students. We found several key patterns that emerged as barriers first-year international students face in the United States. These patterns are summarized into four major categories discussed below. They include academic challenges, social and emotional adaptability, cultural clashes, and relationships with domestic students.

4.1. Academic challenges

Academic challenges are described as the students' experiences with teaching and learning processes. Our data revealed that teaching practices including workload, teaching structure, and format of classes are major issues that students consider challenging in their first year. Students compared these with the educational system and structure in their home countries as well as with their high school context. For example, in describing the teaching practice, a student mentioned: "You really need to do more...you can't just go to class, watch the lecture and you are done. You need to do it more by yourself." Commenting on workload and structure, one student mentioned: "The first week it is just introducing something. There is no assignment you actually do by yourself. But now, they are just kind of overlapping the schedule and so many dues in deadline." Similarly, another student indicated:

The schedule here is more of, the deadlines for different assignments is on different days, according to which program or which course you are taking. In [my home country]...there is a deadline, on the same day, for literally everything or a deadline week which will have all the exams and deadlines together. You can really figure out what you are going to do first, or what you are going to take time so you can start before that. Here it feels a little disorganized.

Being involved in a new academic system and adapting to new teaching styles represent a challenge for international students. They became used to a particular educational system and must now adapt to different processes and expectations.

4.2. Social and Emotional Adaptability

Social and emotional adaptability accounts for challenges students encounter in adjusting to their new society and processing emotional matters such as being away from home/family, taking responsibility for self, and making connections with others. For example, a student said: "Being away from home, trying to meet people" has been the most difficult aspect of beginning school in a different country. Students recognize that one major difference between themselves and the U.S. students is their access to family. This is not only with regard to being able to visit but also the feeling of having someone close to support them in case of an emergency. Another student described the challenge of being away from family members and taking responsibility, saying:

There are things that you don't consider when living with your parents, because they are just there, available to you. Doing your laundry, or maybe

doing the dishes, these are things that you don't really add on till you think you're just going to study, that's it. But then at home, there are parents who are doing your laundry, the dishes, or waking you up on time, making sure you're studying, making sure you are getting good grades, but here you are kind of responsible for whatever you do.

With regard to making connections with others, a student said: “There are always stereotypes about every community...so we are not sure how people might perceive us or treat us. I think that induces a little bit of nervousness. And kind of prohibits us from talking to people here.” This concern likely makes it harder to form friendships with domestic students, which is explored further in section 4.4.

4.3. Cultural Clashes

Cultural clashes describe the challenges experienced by the participants in terms of cultural differences. The most prevalent observations shared by students include interacting with the people, food, community, and language. As an example of clashes in interacting with people, a student said: “I think when international students come here, the biggest problem that they face is that here, people are more individualistic...our home countries are more collective.” Another student stated:

There are people from almost every country in the world, you have to be more open-minded- and respect[ful]. For example, in [my country], if we don't have too many black people, you have to respect black people here, you don't want to get in trouble, and so on, people from all backgrounds, definitely, you first have to be respectful of everyone.

With regard to food, one student said: “In [my country], we eat rice but when I got here...The rice is very strange.” For students this represents a challenge because they consider food to be such an important aspect of life that not being able to find the food they like might affect other aspects of their academic life.

Regarding community, another student said: “[city] was...I thought it was bigger city.” While location and communities may be diverse, the latter excerpt represents the cultural shock for first-year international students who arrive to smaller communities from large cities.

Language was found to be a prevalent challenge, as in our data, most international students expressed this challenge. For example, a student shared:

I am taking chemistry right now, which is also kind of a big challenge, because I had to go to learn all the chemistry rules again. Because it is now in English, it is no longer in Spanish...went back to the basics of chemistry to be able to be at the same level with everybody.

4.4. Relationships with Domestic Students

Relationships with domestic students represent perceptions of international students regarding their interactions with students from the United States. Our data showed

that first year international students experience difficulties developing relationships with domestic students. For example, a student said:

I'm the person who spoke pretty much in the class and American just like silent. Sometime they do, but not always, so that not reach my expectation. Yes, so that's the thing. I hope everyone engage more in the class.

As another example, one student mentioned: "Americans in general, they have a much harder time socializing than [my nationality]." Commenting further on the challenge of interacting with domestic students, another student said: "In our group...we can rely on each other more than we could on local students or American students." For many international students this is an important factor and many of the students interviewed expressed that they would like to have more friends from the United States.

5. DISCUSSION

This work used a qualitative approach to answer the following research question: How do international students identify the barriers faced in their first year of college in the United States? Data indicate that the most prevalent barriers first-year international students experience fall within the themes of academic challenges, social and emotional adaptability, cultural clashes, and relationships with domestic students. Academically, students indicated that course logistics and requirements varied from their previous experiences. In addition to transitioning into the increased responsibilities required of all new university students, international students must adjust to a very different way of teaching and learning than was experienced previously. Socially and emotionally, international students must navigate new relationships in a different culture and with less direct family support. The awareness of cultural differences and stereotypes adds an additional layer of worry to students as they embark upon building new relationships while sometimes also navigating new language demands. Culturally, some of the participants noted explicit differences between habits among students from individualistic societies versus collectivist societies. These differences can impact how interpersonal relationships are created, how school projects are completed, and how different students prioritize their time. Also, participants often discussed how food options or lack thereof contributed to feelings of homesickness. While participants indicated a desire to make more domestic friends, many described difficulties facilitating those connections. All of the factors listed above play an important role in students' academic success.

Study results lead to multiple implications for first-year programs to consider when serving an international student population in order to create a stronger sense of belonging. Firstly, though findings showed that international students are aware of support resources available on campus, few are utilizing those resources. Therefore, it would be beneficial for academic programs to more thoroughly share the potential benefits of available resources with this population of students. Secondly, it is important that instructors, advisors, and other university professionals be briefed on

the various cultural experiences and expectations of international students in order to better understand the extreme transition these students experience as they begin university. This should include discussion of the social and emotional impact students experience when attending university abroad. Thirdly, universities would benefit from providing a space in which international students can share their cultural experiences and surprises. Lastly, as a benefit to both international and domestic students, it would be useful to provide more explicit opportunities for international and domestic students to network with one another.

6. FUTURE WORK

We plan to continue our research to gain further insight into the barriers international students face. Additionally, we plan to implement additional programming that will incorporate the recommendations listed above to provide these students with a stronger sense of belonging. Specifically, we plan to provide international students in the near future with more information about academic expectations in the United States and more detailed information on available resources. Furthermore, we plan to continue sharing our findings with the engineering education community.

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